

GS 80 SPHINX
SAMPLING PROGRAM NOV. - DEC. 1980

1. BED 1 ROCK
2. BED 2 SHALEY UNIT (LOWER)
3. BED 2 MASSIVE ROCK
4. BED 3 SHALEY UNIT (LOWER)
5. BED 3 MASSIVE ROCK
6. BED 4 SHALEY UNIT (LOWER)
7. BED 4 MASSIVE ROCK
8. BED 5 SHALEY UNIT (LOWER)
9. BED 5 MASSIVE ROCK
10. BED 6 SHALEY UNIT (LOWER)
11. BED 6 MASSIVE ROCK
12. BED 7 SHALEY UNIT (LOWER)
13. BED 7 MASSIVE ROCK
14. BED 8 LOWER
15. BED 8 UPPER
16. RUMP PASSAGE SCRAPPING WHITE CRUST - TOP ✓
17. " " " " " MIDDLE ✓
18. " " " " " BOTTOM near water ✓
19. RUMP PASSAGE, WATER ✓
20. WATER SHAFT (THROUGH CAUSEWAY) - WATER
21. MORTAR SAMPLES
 - REFERENCE - STORE, S.T. C.B.S, V.T., G.P.
 - PHASE I - RUMP PASSAGE
 - PHASE II - NW CORNER
 - PHASE III - N-NE
 - PHASE IA - S FOREPAW, CHEST STONWORK
22. CORE BLOCKS, S.T.
CORE BLOCKS, V.T. ?
23. PHASE I BLOCK W. DURIC CRUST